

Extraction chromatographic studies of uranium(VI) with crosslinked poly(acrylic acid) coated on silica gel

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Abstract : A selective method has been developed for extraction and separation of U^{VI} with the chemically synthesized high molecular mass crosslinked poly(acrylic acid) coated on silanized silica gel. The coated materials act as a stationary phase for the extraction chromatographic studies. The structure and thermal stability of crosslinked poly(acrylic acid) has been elucidated with the help of FTIR and TGA. The optimum pH range for quantitative extraction of uranium was found to be 4 to 6. The effects of pH and stripping agent on extraction and elution of U^{VI} have been investigated. Ion exchange and break-through capacity of the exchanger (polymer coated on silanized silica gel) have been determined at room temperature. Surface morphology of the exchanger was studied by SEM. U^{VI} has been separated quantitatively from various synthetic aqueous mixtures containing metal ions (V^{IV} , Th^{IV} , Ce^{IV} , Pb^{II} , Hg^{II} , In^{III} , Fe^{III} and Zr^{IV}) commonly present in uranium ores and fission products. The method permits pre-concentration and sequential separation of U^{VI} from Ce^{VI} , Th^{IV} and Zr^{IV} of the same analytical group. A plausible mechanism for uranium ion exchange has been suggested.

Keywords : Poly(acrylic acid), silanized silica gel, metal ion, ion-exchange, solid phase extraction.

Introduction

Solid phase extraction¹ (SPE) (extraction chromatography) is one of the most efficient techniques since it is fast, simple and cost effective. SPE is based on the utilization of a solid support, coated or immobilized with different materials¹ such as polyelectrolyte, high molecular mass carboxylic acid, chelating agent, surfactant, quaternary ammonium salt, etc. Silica gel is found to act as a successful support since it does not swell or strain, has good mechanical strength and can undergo heat treatment¹. Quite a good amount of literature appears to deal with polymer on the silica support for selective separation of metal ions². U, Th, Zr, Ti, V and Ce belong to same analytical group³. The work on nuclear fission requires complete separation of U^{VI} from uranium and thorium ores, minerals and fission products⁴. Considerable technological importance of uranium is due to its role in the nuclear fuel cycle. There are several reports in literature on the extraction of U^{VI} using solvent extraction with Alamine-336 and T.O.P.O mixture⁵, and *N,N*-dialkyl aliphatic amide⁶. But most of these solvent extraction methods suffer from difficulties due to emulsion formation. Extraction chromatographic studies of U^{VI} with Aliquat-336⁷ have been reported, however, the selectivity and exchange capacity of the materials used are relatively poor. The crosslinked poly(acrylic acid) is widely used in the retention and recovery of heavy

metal ions⁸⁻¹². The crosslinked chelating resin (RNH-DVB) has been applied for the recovery of uranium from sea water¹³. However, crosslinked poly(acrylic acid) (X-PAA), coated on silanized silica gel has not yet been reported. These reports have encouraged us to undertake the investigation on the extraction chromatographic studies of U^{VI} with the crosslinked and coated poly(acrylic acid).

The present paper reports the systematic studies on extraction chromatographic behaviour of U^{VI} and its separation from synthetic mixtures containing metal ions commonly present in thorium and uranium ores with the help of crosslinked poly(acrylic acid) (coated on silanized silica gel).

Results and discussion

Effect of pH on U^{VI} extraction :

The extraction of U^{VI} was studied in the pH range 2.5–6.5 (Fig. 1) using 0.1 M acetate buffer, when, the quantitative extraction of U^{VI} was found over pH 4–6. The complete retention of U^{VI} in the resin bed was found at a flow rate of 1.0 mL min⁻¹. Common anions like Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} and NO_3^- did not interfere in the extraction. In acetate buffer medium (pH 4–6), the uranium ion (UO_2^{2+}) remained in equilibrium (eq. 1) as :

Owing to its suitable size and positive charge, the ionic species (UO_2Ac^+) was retained by the exchange as per following (eq. 2) :

The absence of sharp peak at 1700 cm^{-1} and appearance of a new peak at 1595 cm^{-1} in the FTIR spectrum of uranium adsorbed exchanger indicated the presence of carboxylate anion¹⁴ in the metal ion loaded sample. At low pH (<4.0), the equilibrium (eq. 2) shifted to left. As a result, quantitative extraction of UO_2^{2+} did not take place at low pH; while the ion passed through the column along with the mobile phase at $\text{pH} \leq 3$. While at high pH (>6.0), the uranium ion hydrolysed and did not participate in the exchange process (eq. 2).

Fig. 1. Extraction (%) of U^{VI} as function of pH at room temperature.

Selection of eluent for U^{VI} and diverse metal ions :

The systematic studies on stripping gave the quantitative elution of U^{VI} with $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 (\geq 0.005 \text{ M})$, $\text{HNO}_3 (\geq 0.005 \text{ M})$, $\text{HCl} (\geq 0.015 \text{ M})$ and $\text{CH}_3\text{COOH} (\geq 0.4 \text{ M})$. The $0.01 \text{ M H}_2\text{SO}_4$ was found to be the best stripping agent (eluent) because it required the least volume for elution than by equal concentration of nitric acid, hydrochloric acid and acetic acid. The elution process

followed the reverse reaction of extraction (eq. 2). Efficiency of organic acid (acetic acid) is less than that of the inorganic acids (H_2SO_4 , HNO_3 and HCl) due to its weak complex formation ability. Nitric acid is more effective than hydrochloric acid because of higher complex formation ability of nitrate ion than chloride ion with uranium ion at room temperature¹⁵. The complex formation ability of different anions with UO_2^{2+} follows the order¹⁵ : $\text{SO}_4^{2-} > \text{NO}_3^- > \text{Cl}^- > \text{CH}_3\text{COO}^-$. These eluents were used through out the experiments. The stripping behaviour of diverse metal ions has been examined with various inorganic and organic acids at their different concentration levels.

Pre-concentration and recovery of uranium ions :

The pH of the exchanger in column was adjusted at 5. One mL of U^{6+} (2.62 mg) was mixed with 10 mL of buffer at desired pH 5 and was passed through the column in each loadings. During ten successive loading, uranium ion has been accumulated gradually on the resin bed. Finally, the extracted ion was stripped with $0.01 \text{ M H}_2\text{SO}_4$ (25 mL). The pre-concentration factor (P.F) with subsequent recovery of U^{VI} (Table 1) indicated a high degree of extraction and recovery of U^{VI} .

Method of U^{VI} separation from binary synthetic mixtures :

It was possible to separate U^{VI} from several other metal ions present in binary mixture by exploiting the differences in pH for extraction and by using selective stripping agents. Each binary aqueous mixture was prepared by mixing an aliquot of standard solution of U^{VI} (2.62 mg mL^{-1}) and one of the other metal ions in acetate buffer solution (10 mL) at desired pH (A to H, Table 2). When binary mixture containing either C (U^{VI} with Fe^{III}) or E (U^{VI} / Zr^{IV}) was passed through the column at pH 2.5, both Fe^{III} and Zr^{IV} were extracted in the bed and U^{VI} was passed through the column unretained. The retention of iron and zirconium, and exclusion of uranium may be due to charge difference

Table 1. Pre-concentration and recovery of uranium ions

Column = $0.8 \times 8 \text{ cm}$; flow rate = 1.0 mL min^{-1} ; pH = 5.0; temp. = $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$

Uranium solution passed (mL)	Initial concentration of uranium in the influent, C_i (mg/mL)	Eluent used ($0.01 \text{ M H}_2\text{SO}_4$) (mL)	Concentration of uranium ions in the effluent, C_e (mg/mL)	Recovery (%)	P.F (C_e/C_i)
110	0.238	25	1.038	99.0	4.36

Table 2. Separations of U^{VI} from metal ions mixtures
 U^{VI} taken = 2.62 mg; column = 0.8 × 8 cm; flow rate = 1.0 mL min⁻¹;
 pH = 5.0; *pH = 2.5; temp. = 25 °C

Mixtures	Cations	Added (mg)	Average recovery (%)	Eluent used (M)	Eluent vol. (mL)
A	U ^{VI}	2.62	99.23	0.4 CH ₃ COOH	70
	Ce ^{IV}	3.39	100.88	0.1 CH ₃ COOH	75
B	U ^{VI}	2.62	100.76	0.4 CH ₃ COOH	70
	Th ^{IV}	3.75	100.80	3.0 CH ₃ COOH	80
C	U ^{VI}	2.62	100.38	–	–
	*Zr ^{IV}	2.47	99.59	8.5 HNO ₃	80
D	U ^{VI}	2.62	100.38	0.4 CH ₃ COOH	70
	V ^{IV}	2.06	99.02	0.1 CH ₃ COOH	80
E	U ^{VI}	2.62	99.61	–	–
	*Fe ^{III}	3.41	99.41	0.5 HNO ₃	40
F	U ^{VI}	2.62	100.76	0.005 HNO ₃	80
	In ^{III}	2.81	99.28	0.02 HNO ₃	60
G	U ^{VI}	2.62	100.38	0.01 H ₂ SO ₄	25
	Pb ^{II}	2.18	99.08	0.01 HNO ₃	50
H	U ^{VI}	2.62	100.76	0.01 H ₂ SO ₄	25
	Hg ^{II}	4.02	99.50	0.05 H ₂ SO ₄	70
I	U ^{VI}	2.62	100.38	0.4 CH ₃ COOH	70
	Th ^{IV}	3.75	99.20	3.0 CH ₃ COOH	80
	*Zr ^{IV}	2.47	99.19	8.5 HNO ₃	80
J	V ^{IV}	2.06	100.97	0.1 CH ₃ COOH	80
	U ^{VI}	2.62	99.23	0.4 CH ₃ COOH	70
	Th ^{IV}	3.75	100.80	3.0 CH ₃ COOH	80
K	Ce ^{VI}	3.39	99.70	0.1 CH ₃ COOH	75
	U ^{VI}	2.62	98.85	0.4 CH ₃ COOH	70
	Th ^{IV}	3.75	101.06	3.0 CH ₃ COOH	80
	*Zr ^{IV}	2.47	100.40	8.5 HNO ₃	80

Each value is average of three determinations.

of the metal ions. The effective charge of the hydrated metal ions at pH 2.5 follows the order^{15,16}: Zr^{IV} (+8) > Fe^{III} (+4) > U^{VI} (+2). Extracted Fe^{III} and Zr^{IV} were eluted with 0.5 M HNO₃ and 8.5 M HNO₃ respectively.

At pH 5.0, metal ions Ce^{IV}, Th^{IV}, V^{IV}, In^{III}, Pb^{II} and Hg^{II} were extracted quantitatively along with U^{VI} from their respective aqueous binary mixtures (A to H except C and E). Bivalent diverse metal ions Pb^{II} (G) and Hg^{II} (H) were eluted quantitatively with 0.01 M HNO₃ and 0.05 M H₂SO₄ respectively and trivalent In^{III} (F) with 0.02 M HNO₃. Similarly tetravalent metal ions Ce^{IV} (A), V^{IV} (D) and Th^{IV} (B) were eluted quantitatively with 0.1, 0.1 and 3.0 M CH₃COOH respectively. Extracted U^{VI} was eluted with 0.01 M H₂SO₄, 0.005 M HNO₃ and 0.4

M CH₃COOH (A to H except C and E). Required volume of each eluent is given in the Table 2. After extraction the metal ions were determined complexometrically¹⁷.

Application of the developed method :

In order to assess the possible analytical applications the proposed method was applied to separate U^{VI} from multi-component synthetic aqueous mixtures containing U^{VI} with different metal ions that are commonly found in ores and typical fission product (I to K, Table 2). A clean separation of U^{VI} from ternary (J) and quaternary (K) synthetic aqueous mixtures are exhibited by representative elution curves (Figs. 2 and 3). Results showed high degree of effectiveness and utility of the proposed method.

Fig. 2. The elution profile of V^{IV}, U^{VI} and Th^{IV} mixture.

Fig. 3. The elution profile of *Zr^{IV}, Ce^{IV}, U^{VI} and Th^{IV} mixture.

Experimental

Materials :

Acrylic acid (AA) (Qualigens, Mumbai, India), sodium lauryl sulphate (Glaxo, Mumbai, India), *N,N*-methylene bisacrylamide (MBA) (Fluka, Buchs, Switzerland), ammonium persulphate (APS) (S.d. fine Chem., Boisar, India), UO₂(NO₃)₂ (AnalaR, B.D.H., Mumbai, India), silica gel (Mesh 120) (Qualigens, Mumbai, India), hexamine (S.d. fine Chem., Boisar, India), dimethyl dichlorosilane (Merck, Mumbai, India), methanol (Bengal Chemicals, Kolkata) and ascorbic acid (B.D.H., Mumbai, India) were used as received.

Characterization :

Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectra of the polymer were recorded on Shimadzu FTIR (Model 8400 S, Tokyo, Japan) in the range 4000–400 cm⁻¹ using KBr pellet. An Elico LI-120 pH meter, thermostat and chromatographic column (i.d 0.8 cm) were used. Ion exchange and break-through capacity of the prepared exchanger were determined¹⁸. Scanning electron micrograph (SEM) recorded on a camera (S-570, Japan). Thermal analysis was done by Perkin-Elmer thermal analyser in nitrogen atmosphere at a thermal gradient of 10 °C/min.

Preparation of crosslinked poly(acrylic acid) and development of ion-exchanger material :

The polymerisation was carried out in a three-necked round bottom flask that was kept in a constant temperature (70 °C) water bath¹⁹. Acrylic acid (1 mL) (monomer), distilled water (10 mL) and sodium lauryl sulphate (1 g) (surfactant) were taken in a flask and mixed well by a magnetic stirrer. Pure nitrogen was passed through the solution for 30 min. *N,N*-Methylene-bis-acrylamide (0.5 g) (cross-linker) and ammonium persulphate (1 g) (initiator) were then added and stirred. After two hours, the precipitated white polymer was collected by filtration, washed with distilled water and dried under vacuum until constant weight. Silica gel (25 g) was silanized (SSG)¹⁸ by exposing it to the vapour of dimethyl dichlorosilane (2.5 mL) in nitrogen atmosphere and then washed with methanol and dried. The chemically treated gel was then impregnated with the synthesised cross-linked poly(acrylic acid) solution (18%) in benzene and dried in a rotary vacuum evaporator for uniform coating, as confirmed by SEM. The exchanger was washed with distilled water and dried. Ion exchanger bed was prepared by usual method¹⁸.

Physico-chemical characteristics of the ion-exchanger :

The exchange capacity of the prepared exchanger was found to be 2.52 meq H⁺ g⁻¹ at 25 °C. The value is superior to the reported^{18,20} values, 1.96, 2.40 and 0.57 meq H⁺ g⁻¹ at 25 °C for SRS-100, Versatic-10 and Aliquat-336⁷ respectively. The breakthrough capacity of the prepared exchanger was 33.54 mg U^{VI} per g of dry exchanger at pH 5. The exchanger is thermally stable up to 150 °C and chemically unaffected by different dilute acids. Density of the crosslinked poly(acrylic acid) was found 1.2 g cm⁻³. SEM photograph confirmed the porous nature of X-PAA is (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. SEM photograph of developed ion-exchanger.

Table 3. Assignment of IR peaks

Peak position (cm ⁻¹)	Nature of peak (intensity)	Peak assignment
1200–1240	Broad, medium intensity	C–C long skeleton, C–O stretching ^{14–21}
1640	Sharp, strong intensity	Carbonyl stretching of a secondary amide ^{14,21}
1700–1720	Sharp, strong intensity	Carbonyl stretching of carboxylic acid ^{14,21}
2880	Sharp, strong intensity	C–H stretching of an alkane ¹⁴
2900	Sharp, strong intensity	Hydrogen bonded -OH group of carboxylic acid ²¹
3360	Broad, medium intensity	N–H stretching of an amide ²¹

Chemical nature of the ion-exchanger :

The FTIR spectrum showed several characteristic peaks, the position and their assignment^{14,21} of peaks is given in Table 3. Thus, the synthesized polymer contained both amide (1640 cm⁻¹) and carboxylic acid group (1700 cm⁻¹), and, these are the characteristic features of bisacrylamide crosslinked poly(acrylic acid)^{9–11}.

Structure of crosslinked poly(acrylic acid)

Poly(acrylic acid), [-CH₂-CH(COOH)-]_n is highly soluble in aqueous medium²². However, the synthesised polymer is completely insoluble in water but soluble in benzene. The insolubility may be attributed to the presence of cross-linking in the poly(acrylic acid). The hardness of the polymer is increased with the increase of cross-linker (*N,N*-methylene bis acrylamide).

General extraction procedure :

The prepared ion-exchanger (solid) was loaded in the chromatographic column (i.d 0.8 cm) to achieve a bed height of 8 cm. The exchanger bed was washed with 2 M HCl to remove excess benzene (organic solvent). Acetate buffer of pH 5.0 was passed through the exchanger bed continuously till the effluent pH achieves its constant value at pH 5.0. An aliquot of U^{VI} in acetate buffer at pH 5.0 was passed through the column at a flow rate of 1.0 mL min⁻¹. After extraction, U^{VI} was eluted with suitable eluents and the amount of U^{VI} in each fraction was determined complexometrically¹⁷.

Conclusions :

The proposed method is simple, rapid, selective and economic. Complete separation and estimation could be done in 2.5 h. The exchange and breakthrough capacity of the proposed cation exchanger are considerably higher than the commercially available Versatic-10, SRS-100 and Aliquat-336. The exchanger functions well over the temperature range 20–40 °C and pH range 4–6 for uranium. Clear separation of U^{VI} has been achieved from several other metal ions (Fe^{III}, Zr^{IV}, Ce^{IV}, Th^{IV}, Hg^{II}, Pb^{II}, In^{III} and V^{IV}). Very minute amount (~0.14 g/g silica gel) of extractant in the developed exchanger can selectively separate U^{VI} from wide variety of synthetic mixtures containing large number of heavy, toxic and conger cations. The exchanger is chemically stable (up to 8.5 M HNO₃, 4 M CH₃COOH, 4 M HCl and 2 M H₂SO₄), effective over a wide range of pH and can be used for more than 30–40 cycles without any loss of its exchange capacity. These show its additional advantages over the other conventional exchangers^{8–13}. Results obtained were satisfactory and recovery of Fe^{III}, Zr^{IV}, Ce^{IV}, Th^{IV}, Hg^{II}, Pb^{II}, In^{III} and V^{IV} were quantitative. The method is quite reproducible with low standard deviation (>0.08) and an average of three determinations was taken. The recovered amount was compared with the known amount of added metal ions and the accuracy was found to be within ±1%.

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